

Researcher Engagement & Data Group

2025 Annual Report

Advanced Research Computing

We provide services including:

- High Performance Computing
- Secure Storage
- Training in Research Computing
- Research Software Engineers (RSEs)
- Research Data Management

BEAR (Birmingham Environment for Academic Research) services offer an excellent foundation for research*

Prestigious Hugh Huxton

Find out more about BEAR services

www.birmingham.ac.uk/bear

♥ BEAR

★ FREESTORAGE ★

Stephanie Thompson, Aslam Ghumra, Debbie Carter & Yajie Zhang – bearinfo@contacts.bham.ac.uk

Advanced Research Computing, University of Birmingham, February 2026

Annual Report

2025

Introduction

The Researcher Engagement and Data Group (REDG) within Advanced Research Computing (ARC) is comprised of 3.3FTE posts and engages with researchers across the University of Birmingham, from postgraduate level to senior academics, to ensure that they are aware of all the advanced computing facilities available to them through [BEAR services](#), as well as supporting their use through training workshops, 1:1 sessions and online learning materials. The team members are:

- Dr Stephanie Thompson – Researcher Engagement & Data Group Leader
- Aslam Ghumra – Research Data Management Specialist
- Debbie Carter – Research Training and Engagement Officer
- Yajie Zhang – Training Coordinator

1573

People engaged with us at events/inductions

Highlights of 2025

- Winning 5 years of funding to extend training provision
- A 30% increase in the number of people we engaged with compared to 2024
- Coordinating a [successful HPC Wire Award for Best Use of AI Methods](#)
- The [BEAR Challenge](#) was expanded to 15 teams, and a team won the national CIUK Cluster Challenge
- Increasing reach of our training to the College of Social Sciences (CoSS) and College of Arts and Law (CAL)

Collaborations within UoB

- The BEAR Champion voluntary group continues to expand, with [ten new BEAR Champions joining in 2025](#). They met regularly, providing feedback on BEAR services and helping with training and outreach
- The 14th [BEAR Conference](#) in May had its highest attendance for years, featuring two compelling keynote speakers, and PGRs describing a wide variety of research enabled by High Performance Computing
- REDG met regularly with the Library, Graduate/Doctoral School, and other researcher developer support staff
- Stephanie is a UoB Sustainability Champion, is in the Digital Sustainability team, and Green Week Planning Committee
- Debbie is a member of the IT Services People & Culture Working Group

215

People attended either a drop-in or 1:1 session

Outreach

- We gave talks at 21 sessions to raise awareness of training and services, including at five School/Research Committee meetings and the CAL PGR Induction
- In total, REDG engaged with over 1,500 researchers via stands at events and talks. We also met with 215 people from all 5 colleges on a 1:1 basis to support their use of BEAR services, with the most common query being about storage
- [We ran a session on 'Data and AI for researchers'](#) at the University's first Data Conference

532

People attended our training workshops

Training

- 15 different [training workshops](#) (see Appendix) were delivered at regular intervals over the year with 32 workshops held in total (5 online) and 532 attendees, 37% more than in 2024
- 5 new workshops were delivered, with 4 developed by RSEs. Several more workshops are currently in development to be delivered throughout 2026
- The no-show rate for training reduced by a third due to the implementation of a 'black list', from a peak of 42% in 2022 to just 14% in 2025
- Attendance from CoSS and CAL has increased, with R for Social Sciences and Introduction to Computational Thinking proving popular (see Appendix)
- Training webpages were revised, splitting the workshops into sections to aid navigation
- The training feedback form was simplified to encourage completion, which resulted in nearly 3x more completed feedback forms for 2025 vs 2024
- Training appears to be highly effective with confidence levels in the topic being taught after workshops increasing from an average of 8% feeling confident prior to training, to an average of 84% after training

757

New enrolments on our Canvas courses in 2025

Communications

- The most popular blog posts out of 60 published in 2025 were '[Recruiting three RSEs](#)' and a [case study on using BlueBEAR](#)
- ARC's support of the 'Beariables' team that won the CIUK Cluster Challenge was featured in a [University student story](#), and use of BlueBEAR and the HPC Wire Award was featured in the University Briefing to all staff in November
- [27 case studies](#) were compiled and published on our blog, featuring research from every college

External outreach

- Stephanie gave talks on training and outreach at [RSE Midlands 2025](#) and [STEP-UP RS London 2025](#), was on a panel at the HPC-SIG in Cambridge for 'Research Data Storage management in UK Academia in 2025', and on the stand at CIUK representing the HPC-SIG
- The team participated in the following Committees/Groups:
 - Aslam – DRI Retreat Advisory Committee
 - Stephanie – [HPC-SIG Committee](#) (EDIA Officer), Green DiSC Research Computing Infrastructure Working Group

Conclusion

This year the expansion of our training workshop programme to new areas of the University has been the most noticeable achievement, along with increasing our engagement both internally and externally. It has been great to see other institutions employ research computing engagement roles, and we look forward to sharing knowledge over the coming year. Sustainable research computing is becoming an increasingly hot topic, and we will be continuing to raise awareness of what we are doing in this area ([summary here](#)), and supporting researchers to become certified in the Green DiSC digital sustainability scheme. Lastly, whilst senior academics have recently fed their needs into the Digital Strategy via working groups, all researchers will be asked to give feedback on support for active research via the 2026 [IT Needs of Active Research survey](#).

13,396

Total page views of our blog posts

Appendix

Figure 1 Registrations for training workshops in 2025 per college.

Registration for training workshops came from researchers across all colleges and was on average highest from the college of Engineering and Physical Sciences, and lowest from the college of Arts and Law. For individual workshops, R programming language workshops were most popular with the college of Life and Environmental Sciences and Social Sciences, whereas all others were most popular with EPS.

Colleges and values in brackets = CMH – Medicine and Health (108), COSS – Social Sciences (72), LES – Life & Environmental Sciences (131), EPS – Engineering and Physical Sciences (261), CAL – Arts and Law (32), PS = Professional Services staff (16).

Workshops delivered over 2025:

1	Introduction to Linux	9	NEW – Advanced R Topics - Reproducible Research with R
2	Introduction to BlueBEAR	10	NEW – Intermediate Research Software Development
3	Advanced BlueBEAR	11	NEW – R for Social Sciences
4	Software Carpentry – Python	12	NEW – Introducing Computational Thinking
5	Software Carpentry – R	13	NVIDIA DLI Fundamentals of Deep Learning Workshop
6	Software Carpentry – MATLAB	14	NEW – NVIDIA Fundamentals of Accelerated Computing with CUDA Python
7	Software Carpentry – Git	15	NVIDIA Fundamentals of Accelerated Computing with Modern CUDA C++
8	Data Carpentry – Image Processing with Python		